

Regulation of glucose insulin metabolism using feedback linearization

Meriem Samai, Ghedjati Keltoum, Abdelaziz Mourad

Automatic Laboratory, Department of Automation and Intelligent Systems, Faculty of Technology, University of Sétif, Setif, Algeria

Article Info

Article history:

Received Jun 13, 2024

Revised Jun 11, 2025

Accepted Aug 1, 2025

Keywords:

Artificial pancreas
Glucose-insulin
Lyapunov stability
System regulation
Virtual linearization

ABSTRACT

Diabetes is a chronic disease that occurs when the pancreas does not produce enough insulin, or when the body is not able to effectively use the insulin it produces. Insulin is a hormone that regulates blood sugar levels, this regulation is done by the pancreas. When this organ is damaged, the patient will have to regulate its blood sugar level themselves. This task is really painful and we will have to resort to an artificial pancreas or we will have to design a regulator which stabilizes blood sugar at its basal value. Several controls have been developed and the objective of this paper is to use input output linearization technique to regulate blood glucose levels by injecting an adequate quantity of insulin. The glucose insulin metabolism is a non-linear system whose input is the quantity of insulin to be injected and the output is the blood glucose measured in the blood. Simulations examples are given to demonstrate the usefulness of the command developed.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Abdelaziz Mourad

Automatic Laboratory, Department of Automation and Intelligent Systems, Faculty of Technology

University of Sétif

UN1901, Setif, Algeria

Email: abde_m@yahoo.fr

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the major diseases in the Western world today is diabetes. Several million people suffer from the disease and the number is increasing. Culture is mainly due to the lifestyle in the western world, with lots of unhealthy food. Because it's a big problem, many researchers are trying to find ways to diagnose and treat disease. One approach is to design a mathematical model describing the glucose-insulin system. Diabetes is a malfunction of this system. These mathematical models can be used to diagnose, but also to create simulators to test various types of treatment. One of the mathematical models describing the glucose-insulin system with a small number of parameters is called minimal model of Bergman, it was introduced in the eighties [1]. This is the model that will be described and analyzed in this paper. To regulate the glucose level, Menani *et al.* [2] use the positive sliding mode control and Menani [3] the intelligent control is used. Ali and Padhi [4], the optimal control is used to regulate the blood glucose. Kaveh and Shtessel [5] the high order sliding mode control is applied. Another technique that means the predictive control is used by the authors in [6], [7]. The fuzzy logic which is known that it approximate nonlinear function is used in [8] to blood glucose regulation. Chui [9], an artificial pancreas is used and an algorithm has been developed. Seron *et al.* [10] tried to do a between several model predictive control in realistic and stochastic environment for patients of type 1 diabetes. Another robust technique that means sliding mode control techniques is used in [11]. Campos-Delgado *et al.* [12], the theory of knowledge-based controllers is investigated. Meriem *et al.* [13] use the well-known backstepping technique to regulate the glucose at it's basal value. This regulation is done by injecting an amount of insuling that has been calculated using the previous technique. The insulin glucose metabolism can be regulated using the simple

adaptive control with the condition that this system is almost strictly positive real (ASPR) [14]. Karima and Mourad [15] adopts the principle of saturation that means the amounts of insulin do not take a high value. The results shows that their control laws give a good results and one see that the glucose is regulated within an acceptable time. The fuzzy logic using the mamdani concept is used in [16] where the controller in applied for three patients and the authors claim that the controller give a good result in the sense that the glucose in regulated at a natural values.

The main objective of this study is the realization of an artificial pancreas capable of providing the appropriate dose of insuline independently of the patient, so the latter can lead his life in an adequate way. This artificial pancreas is equipped with alarms in case of hyperglycemia or hypoglycemia. The description of the glucose insulin metabolism is described in [17]. Lewis *et al.* [18] gives two regulation method called the direct and indirect actions. The proportional-integral-derivative (PID) control [19] is used in glucose insulin regulation where the proportional, integral and derivative are changed in order to force the glucose concentration to be in the acceptable values. Riham and Udhayakumar [20] uses the fractional order with time delay to regulate the glucose, the fraction order is a concept where one suppose that the order of the system is fractional where the system order is fractional which is a more general notion than a system with integer order.

The paper is organized as follows. In section 2, one give the input output linearization. The Bergman minimal model is given in section 3. In section 4 one apply the input output (I/O) linearization to regulate the glucose level. Simulations results are given in section 5 and we end this paper with a conclusion in section 6.

2. INPUT OUTPUT LINEARIZATION

Input-output linearization is a recent control technique, it consists of linearizing a non-linear system using a state or output feedback and using a new command. This technique makes it possible to apply well-known linear controls to complicated and non-linear systems. Let's take the non-linear system [21].

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x} = f(x) + g(x)u \\ y = h(x) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Where $x \in R^n$ is the state, $u \in R, y \in R$ are the input output, and suppose that the relative degree of the system is n that means the input appears in the n^{th} derivative of the output, i.e.,

$$\dot{y} = \frac{dh(x)}{dt} = \frac{\partial h(x)}{\partial x} \frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{\partial h(x)}{\partial x} f(x) + \frac{\partial h(x)}{\partial x} g(x)u \quad (2)$$

And using the lie derivative, this expression is given by:

$$\dot{y} = L_f h(x) + L_g h(x)u \text{ with } L_g h(x) = 0 \quad (3)$$

The second derivative is given by:

$$\ddot{y} = \frac{d(L_f h(x))}{dt} = \frac{\partial(L_f h(x))}{\partial x} \frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{\partial(L_f h(x))}{\partial x} f(x) + \frac{\partial(L_f h(x))}{\partial x} g(x)u$$

Which can be written as:

$$\ddot{y} = L_f(L_f h(x)) + L_g(L_f h(x))u$$

That means:

$$\ddot{y} = L_f^2(h(x)) \text{ with } L_g(L_f h(x)) = 0$$

The $(n^{\text{th}}-1)$ derivative is given by:

$$y^{(n-1)} = L_f^{n-1}(h(x)) \text{ with } L_g(L_f^{(n-2)}h(x)) = 0$$

And the n^{th} derivative is given by:

$$y^{(n)} = L_f^n(h(x)) \text{ with } L_g(L_f^{(n-1)}h(x)) \neq 0$$

That means:

$$\begin{cases} y^{(i)} = L_f^i(h(x)); L_g(L_f^{(i-1)}h(x)) = 0; i = 1..n-1 \\ y^{(n)} = L_f^n(h(x)) + L_g(L_f^{(n-1)}h(x))u \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

So, if one take the transformation $\xi_i = y^{(i)}$, one have:

$$\begin{cases} \xi_1 = y \\ \dot{\xi}_1 = \dot{y} = \xi_2 \\ \dot{\xi}_2 = \ddot{y} = \xi_3 \\ \vdots \\ \dot{\xi}_{n-1} = y^{(n-1)} = \xi_n \\ \dot{\xi}_n = y^{(n)} = L_f^n(h(x)) + L_g(L_f^{(n-1)}h(x))u = \alpha(x) + \beta(x)u = v \end{cases}$$

That means, the input output linearization is given by:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\xi}_1 \\ \dot{\xi}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \dot{\xi}_{n-1} \\ \dot{\xi}_n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \xi_1 \\ \xi_2 \\ \vdots \\ \xi_{n-1} \\ \xi_n \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} v; \quad y = \xi_1$$

In linear form, it is given by:

$$\dot{\xi} = A\xi + Bv; y = \xi_1 \quad (5)$$

Where:

$$\xi = [\xi_1 \quad \xi_1 \quad \dots \quad \xi_n]^T$$

It is well know that this form is suitable for regulation and tracking using state feedback. once the command v is synthesized, the actual command u is given by:

$$u = \frac{v - \alpha(x)}{\beta(x)} \text{ with } \beta(x) \neq 0 \quad (6)$$

In this section, one apply the I/O linearization to regulate the glucose for an illness person. This is achieved by searching the amount of insulin to be injected in order to regulate the glucose at it's basal value that means the normal value and one begin by the modelisation of the glucose insulin metabolism. Zakeri and Ozgoli [22], the authors used a state feedback controller to regulate the glucose at it's basal valur, our method is more efficient in terms of response time.

3. BERGMAN MINIMAL MODEL

There are many model of the glucose insulin system, the simple one is called minimal model of Bergman.

a. Mechanisms of blood glucose regulation

The regulation of blood sugar is given by the pancreas and the liver. The pancreas secretes two hormones:

- Glucagon is secreted by Alpha_cells
- Insulin is secreted by Beta_cells

The liver can, depending on the circumstances:

- Store glucose as glycogen when insulin levels increase
- Release glycogen in the form of glucose under the action of glucagon.

The Figure 1 [23] describe the metabolism of the glucose insulin regulation.

b. Description of the Bergman minimal model

The Bergman, minimal model is described by (7)-(9) [1].

$$\dot{G}(t) = -p_1(G(t) - G_b) - X(t)G(t) + D(t) \tag{7}$$

$$X(t) = -p_2X(t) + p_3(I(t) - I_b) \tag{8}$$

$$\dot{I}(t) = -n(I(t) - I_b) + \gamma[G(t) - h]^+ + u(t) \tag{9}$$

$D(t)$ is a disturbance that can be modeled by a decreasing exponential function of the following form: $D(t) = A \exp(-Bt)$, $B > 0$, which represents

1. The meals Fisher standards [24]. $B = 0.05$
2. The effects of exercise [25]. $B = 0.11$

The description of the parameters and terms in (7) to (9) are given in the Table 1.

Figure 1. The know model which describe the glucose_insulin metabolism is given by R. N. Bergman

This model can be used to simulate the glucose-insulin system for a type 1 diabetic on treatment. It can be used to test the predictive controllers models [26] and as a tool in the search for an artificial pancreas. This model also adopts the problem with the minimal model of glucose.

This paragraph summarized the Bergman model, and we see that it is a nonlinear system and complex, and the feedback linearization is the robust tool to deal with such systems. Several regulation methods have been used, the only obstacle is that the Bergman model is not universal and other models exist and continue to be developed and therefore the perspective is to continue working to develop a model of insulin glucose as close as possible to the real patient.

Table 1. Parameters description and terms of the Bergman minimal model

Parameter	Unit	Description
t	min	The time
G(t)	mg/dl	concentration of glucose in the blood
G_b	mg/dl	steady state concentration of glucose in the blood.
X(t)	1/min	the effect of active insulin.
I(t)	$\mu\text{U/ml}$	The concentration of insulin in the blood.
I_b	$\mu\text{U/ml}$	steady state concentration of insulin in the blood.
$I_2(t)$	$\mu\text{U/ml}$	active concentration of insulin
p_1	1/min	independent glucose disposal Speed insulin.
p_2	1/min	release rate of active insulin.
p_3	(min^{-2})	The increase in the ability to absorb caused by insulin
n	1/min	rate of prime insulin decrease in plasma
γ	$(\mu\text{U/ml}) \text{min}^{-2}$	release rate of insulin from pancreatic β -cells after glucose injection to the glucose concentration above the threshold
h	mg/dl	glucose threshold value which the pancreatic β - cells release insulin
u(t)	$\mu\text{U/ml}$	defines the injection of insulin and replaces the normal regulation of insulin of the body

4. GLUCOSE REGULATION USING INPUT-OUTPUT LINEARIZATION

In order to control blood glucose, we need to know the amount of insulin to inject, this operation is only possible if we know the model of glucose-insulin metabolism. Several models are known, ranging from the simplest to the most complicated. The most widespread is Bergman's model. The Bergman minimal model is given by:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{G}(t) = -p_1(G(t) - G_b) - X(t)G(t) + D(t) \\ \dot{X}(t) = -p_2X(t) + p_3(I(t) - I_b) \\ \dot{I}(t) = -p_4(I(t) - I_{b1}) + u(t) \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Let's take:

$$x_1 = G(t); x_2 = X(t); x_3 = I(t) \quad (11)$$

So,

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}_1(t) = -p_1(x_1 - G_b) - x_2x_1 + D(t) \\ \dot{x}_2(t) = -p_2x_2 + p_3(x_3 - I_b) \\ \dot{x}_3(t) = -p_4(x_3 - I_{b1}) + u(t) \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

The error is given by:

$$e = G(t) - G_b = x_1 - G_b \quad (13)$$

It's derivative is given by:

$$\dot{e} = \dot{x}_1 - \dot{G}_b = \dot{x}_1 = -p_1(x_1 - G_b) - x_2x_1 + D(t)$$

The second derivative is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{e} &= -p_1\dot{x}_1 - \dot{x}_2x_1 - x_2\dot{x}_1 + \dot{D}(t) = -(p_1+x_2)\dot{x}_1 - \dot{x}_2x_1 + \dot{D}(t) \\ \ddot{e} &= -(p_1+x_2)[-p_1(x_1 - G_b) - x_2x_1 + D(t)] - [-p_2x_2 + p_3(x_3 - I_b)]x_1 + \dot{D}(t) \end{aligned}$$

The third derivative is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \dddot{e} &= -\dot{x}_2[-p_1(x_1 - G_b) - x_2x_1 + D(t)] \\ &\quad - (p_1+x_2)\left[-p_1\dot{x}_1 - \dot{x}_2x_1 - x_2\dot{x}_1 + \dot{D}(t)\right] \\ &\quad - \left[-p_2\dot{x}_2 + p_3\dot{x}_3\right]x_1 + \\ &\quad - \left[-p_2x_2 + p_3(x_3 - I_b)\right]\dot{x}_1 + \ddot{D}(t) \end{aligned}$$

That means:

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{e} = & -\dot{x}_2[-p_1(x_1 - G_b) - x_2x_1 + D(t)] \\ & - (p_1+x_2)\left[-(p_1+x_2)\dot{x}_1 + \dot{D}(t)\right] + (p_1+x_2)\left[\dot{x}_2 x_1\right] \\ & + \left[p_2\dot{x}_2 - p_3\dot{x}_3\right]x_1 + [p_2x_2 - p_3(x_3 - I_b)]\dot{x}_1 + \ddot{D}(t) \end{aligned}$$

So,

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{e} = & \dot{x}_2[p_1(x_1 - G_b) + x_2x_1 - D(t) + (p_1+x_2)x_1 + p_2x_1] \\ & + (p_1+x_2)\left[(p_1+x_2)\dot{x}_1 - \dot{D}(t)\right] \\ & - p_3\dot{x}_3 x_1 + [p_2x_2 - p_3(x_3 - I_b)]\dot{x}_1 + \ddot{D}(t) \end{aligned}$$

That means:

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{e} = & \dot{x}_2[p_1(x_1 - G_b) + x_2x_1 - D(t) + (p_1+x_2)x_1 + p_2x_1] \\ & + (p_1+x_2)^2 \dot{x}_1 - (p_1+x_2)\dot{D}(t) \\ & - p_3\dot{x}_3 x_1 + [p_2x_2 - p_3(x_3 - I_b)]\dot{x}_1 + \ddot{D}(t) \end{aligned}$$

So,

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{e} = & \dot{x}_2[p_1(x_1 - G_b) + x_2x_1 - D(t) + (p_1+x_2)x_1 + p_2x_1] \\ & + \dot{x}_1\left[(p_1+x_2)^2 + [p_2x_2 - p_3(x_3 - I_b)]\right] - (p_1+x_2)\dot{D}(t) \\ & - p_3[-p_4(x_3 - I_{b1}) + u(t)]\dot{x}_1 + \ddot{D}(t) \end{aligned}$$

The third derivative can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{e} = & [-p_2x_2 + p_3(x_3 - I_b)]\left[p_1(x_1 - G_b) + x_2x_1 - D(t) + (p_1+x_2)x_1 + p_2x_1\right] \\ & + [-p_1(x_1 - G_b) - x_2x_1 + D(t)]\left[(p_1+x_2)^2 + [p_2x_2 - p_3(x_3 - I_b)]\right] - (p_1+x_2)\dot{D}(t) \\ & p_3p_4(x_3 - I_{b1})x_1 - p_3u(t)x_1 + \ddot{D}(t) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

In the form:

$$\ddot{e} = \alpha - pu(t)x_1 \quad (15)$$

Where:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha = & [-p_2x_2 + p_3(x_3 - I_b)]\left[p_1(x_1 - G_b) + x_2x_1 - D(t) + (p_1+x_2)x_1 + p_2x_1\right] \\ & [-p_1(x_1 - G_b) - x_2x_1 + D(t)]\left[(p_1+x_2)^2 + [p_2x_2 - p_3(x_3 - I_b)]\right] - (p_1+x_2)\dot{D}(t) \\ & p_3p_4(x_3 - I_{b1})x_1 + \ddot{D}(t) \end{aligned}$$

Let's take the Hurwitz polynomial.

$$s^3 + \alpha_2 s^2 + \alpha_1 s + \alpha_0 \quad (16)$$

So, the differential equation:

$$\ddot{e} + \alpha_2 \dot{e} + \alpha_1 e + \alpha_0 e = 0 \quad (17)$$

Implies that the error $e(t)$ goes to zero and then $G(t)$ goes to G_b . From the later equation, one have:

$$\ddot{e} = -\alpha_2 \dot{e} - \alpha_1 e - \alpha_0 e = \alpha - pu(t)x_1 \quad (18)$$

And then the command $u(t)$ is given by:

$$u(t) = \frac{\alpha_2 \ddot{e} + \alpha_1 \dot{e} + \alpha_0 e + \alpha}{p_3 x_1} \quad (19)$$

With $pu(t) \neq 0$.

Let's take z_1, z_2 and z_3 as the poles in the feedback loop, so the characteristic polynomial is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} P(s) &= (s - z_1)(s - z_2)(s - z_3) = (s^2 - z_1 s - z_2 s + z_1 z_2)(s - z_3) \\ &= s^3 + s^2(-z_1 - z_2 - z_3) + s(z_2 z_3 + z_1 z_2 + z_1 z_3) - z_1 z_2 z_3 \\ &= s^3 + \alpha_2 s^2 + \alpha_1 s + \alpha \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

So,

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_0 &= -z_1 z_2 z_3 \\ \alpha_1 &= z_2 z_3 + z_1 z_2 + z_1 z_3 \\ \alpha_2 &= -z_1 - z_2 - z_3 \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

5. SIMULATION

In the simulation, it is required that the glucose concentration tracks its basal reference $G_b=80 \text{ mg/dl}$ by injecting the sufficient amount of insulin. One suppose that at $t=250 \text{ min}$ a perturbation is added represented by an intake of carbohydrates of the form $D(t) = A \exp(-Bt), B > 0$. The simulation has been done over 500 min. The initial conditions are given by $p_1 = 0; p_2 = 0.025; p_3 = 0.00013; G_b = 80 \text{ mg/dl}; I_b = 7 \text{ } \mu\text{U/ml}$. The simulation is done over 500 min. And the roots in feedback loop are given by $z_1 = -0.1; z_2 = -0.2; z_3 = -0.3$.

Figure 2 shows the evolution of the glucose concentration of a patient and one see that the controller is able to lead the glucose to its normal value that means $G_b=80 \text{ mg/dl}$ after about 100 min and just the occurrence of the perturbation, the glucose increase and return to its basal value after 75 min. Figure 3 shows the evolution of the insulin which increase if one have a big amount of glucose and return to its basal value once the glucose is in its basal value. Figure 4 shows controlled input which also increase if the amount of glucose is higher and settle to its basal value if the glucose reached its normal value that means $G_b=80 \text{ mg/dl}$.

Figure 2. Glucose concentration for a patient person Figure 3. Concentration of insulin in the blood

Figure 4. Command (insulin injection) to the blood glucose insulin system

6. CONCLUSION

This paper presents at first the adaptive command which will be applied for a perturbed system. The Lyapunov theory has been addressed in order to achieve a robust command against the uncertainty which is inherent in all real systems. The adaptive command has been applied to control the concentration of the glucose of a patient person. The simulation results confirm the robustness of the developed controller.

FUNDING INFORMATION

Authors state no funding involved.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

This journal uses the Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) to recognize individual author contributions, reduce authorship disputes, and facilitate collaboration.

Name of Author	C	M	So	Va	Fo	I	R	D	O	E	Vi	Su	P	Fu
Meriem Samai	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Ghedjati Keltoum		✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	
Abdelaziz Mourad	✓			✓				✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

- | | | |
|-------------------------------|----------------------------|------------------------------------|
| C : C onceptualization | I : I nterpretation | Vi : V isualization |
| M : M ethodology | R : R esources | Su : S upervision |
| So : S oftware | D : D ata Curation | P : P roject administration |
| Va : V alidation | O : O rganizing | Fu : F unding acquisition |
| Fo : F ormal analysis | E : E ditors | |

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

- The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author, [Abdelaziz Mourad]. The data, which contain information that could compromise the privacy of research participants, are not publicly available due to certain restrictions.
- Derived data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author [Abdelaziz Mourad] on request.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. N. Bergman, G. Toffolo, C. R. Bowden, and C. Cobelli, “Minimal Modeling, Partition Analysis, and Identification of Glucose Disposal in Animals and Man.,” *Proceedings - International Conference on Cybernetics and Society*, pp. 129–135, 1980.

- [2] K. Menani, T. Mohammadridha, N. Magdelaine, M. Abdelaziz, and C. H. Moog, "Positive sliding mode control for blood glucose regulation," *International Journal of Systems Science*, vol. 48, no. 15, pp. 3267–3278, Nov. 2017, doi: 10.1080/00207721.2017.1381893.
- [3] K. Menani, "Contribution to Robust Adaptive Control of Physiological Processes by Sliding Mode, Fuzzy Controller and Reference Model (*Contribution à la Commande Adaptative Robuste des Processus Physiologiques par Mode Glissant, Contrôleur Flou et Modèle de Référence*)," Ph.D. dissertation, Université de Sétif, France, 2019.
- [4] S. F. Ali and R. Padhi, "Optimal blood glucose regulation using single network adaptive critics," in *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Control Applications*, IEEE, Jul. 2009, pp. 89–94, doi: 10.1109/CCA.2009.5281091.
- [5] P. Kaveh and Y. Shtessel, "Higher order sliding mode control for blood glucose regulation," in *Proceedings of the 2006 International Workshop on Variable Structure Systems, VSS'06*, IEEE, 2006, pp. 11–16, doi: 10.1109/VSS.2006.1644485.
- [6] M. Nalini, V. Balaji, V. Kumar, R. Priya, A. Ulaganayaki, and S. S. Priya, "Blood glucose regulation system using model predictive controller," in *IEEE International Conference on Innovations in Green Energy and Healthcare Technologies - 2017, IGEHT 2017*, IEEE, Mar. 2017, pp. 1–5, doi: 10.1109/IGEHT.2017.8094062.
- [7] M. C. Oliveira, E. D. Moreno, G. M. A. Da Silva, and O. A. Z. Sotomayor, "Blood Glucose Regulation in Patients with Type 1 Diabetes Using Model Predictive Control and Data Reconciliation," *IEEE Latin America Transactions*, vol. 16, no. 12, pp. 2872–2880, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.1109/TLA.2018.8804251.
- [8] L. Chengwei and H. Ruiqiang, "Fuzzy-PID control for the regulation of blood glucose in diabetes," in *Proceedings of the 2009 WRI Global Congress on Intelligent Systems, GCIS 2009*, IEEE, 2009, pp. 170–174, doi: 10.1109/GCIS.2009.280.
- [9] C. K. Chui, "Blood glucose regulation using an implantable artificial pancreas," in *SAMI 2015 - IEEE 13th International Symposium on Applied Machine Intelligence and Informatics, Proceedings*, IEEE, Jan. 2015, p. 11, doi: 10.1109/SAMI.2015.7061855.
- [10] M. M. Seron, A. M. Mediolio, and G. C. Goodwin, "A methodology for the comparison of traditional MPC and stochastic MPC in the context of the regulation of blood glucose levels in Type 1 diabetes," in *2016 Australian Control Conference, AuCC 2016*, IEEE, Nov. 2017, pp. 126–131, doi: 10.1109/AUCC.2016.7868015.
- [11] P. Kaveh and Y. B. Shtessel, "Blood glucose regulation in diabetics using sliding mode control techniques," in *Proceedings of the Annual Southeastern Symposium on System Theory*, IEEE, 2006, pp. 171–175, doi: 10.1109/ssst.2006.1619068.
- [12] D. U. Campos-Delgado, R. Femat, E. Ruiz-Velázquez, and A. Gordillo-Moscoco, "Knowledge-Based Controllers for Blood Glucose Regulation in Type I Diabetic Patients by Subcutaneous Route," in *IEEE International Symposium on Intelligent Control - Proceedings*, IEEE, 2003, pp. 592–597, doi: 10.1109/isc.2003.1254703.
- [13] S. Meriem, G. Keltoum and A. Mourad, "Glucose Insulin Regulation Using Backstepping Technique," *2022 2nd International Conference on Advanced Electrical Engineering (ICAEE)*, 2022, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/ICAEE53772.2022.9962022.
- [14] S. Meriem, G. Keltoum and A. Mourad, "Extension of Simple Adaptive Control to non ASPR Systems," *2024 2nd International Conference on Electrical Engineering and Automatic Control (ICEEAC), Setif, Algeria, 2024*, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/ICEEAC61226.2024.10576510.
- [15] M. Karima and A. Mourad, "Adaptive Control Design with Saturation Constraints for Different Experimental Glucose Models," *Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Electrical Engineering and Control Applications*, 2024, pp.171-183, doi: 10.1007/978-981-97-0045-5_17.
- [16] P. Thakur, Y. T. Pillay, J. Watkins and E. Sawan, "Type-I Fuzzy Controller for Blood Glucose Regulation in Type-I Diabetic Patients," *SoutheastCon 2024, Atlanta, GA, USA, 2024*, pp. 1205-1209, doi: 10.1109/SoutheastCon52093.2024.10500181.
- [17] L. Norton, C. Shannon, A. Gastaldelli, and R. A. DeFronzo, "Insulin: The master regulator of glucose metabolism," *Metabolism: Clinical and Experimental*, vol. 129, p. 155142, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.metabol.2022.155142.
- [18] G. F. Lewis, A. C. Carpentier, S. Pereira, M. Hahn, and A. Giacca, "Direct and indirect control of hepatic glucose production by insulin," *Cell Metabolism*, vol. 33, no. 4, pp. 709–720, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.cmet.2021.03.007.
- [19] O. Saleem and J. Iqbal, "Complex-order PID controller design for enhanced blood-glucose regulation in Type-I diabetes patients," *Measurement and Control (United Kingdom)*, vol. 56, no. 9–10, pp. 1811–1825, 2023, doi: 10.1177/00202940231189504.
- [20] F. A. Rihan and K. Udhayakumar, "Optimal control of glucose-insulin dynamics via delay differential model with fractional-order," *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, vol. 114, pp. 243–255, Feb. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.aej.2024.11.071.
- [21] A. Isidori, "Nonlinear Control Systems," Part of the Communications and Control Engineering book series (CCE) Springer-Verlag, 1997.
- [22] H. Zakeri and S. Ozgoli, "A polynomial modeling and state feedback control of blood glucose regulatory in diabetic patients," in *ICIAS 2012 - 2012 4th International Conference on Intelligent and Advanced Systems: A Conference of World Engineering, Science and Technology Congress (ESTCON) - Conference Proceedings*, IEEE, Jun. 2012, pp. 388–392, doi: 10.1109/ICIAS.2012.6306224.
- [23] S. Halimi and J. Girard, "Traitement du diabète de type 2. Où en sommes-nous des voies agissant sur le glucagon ? (*Treatment of type 2 diabetes. Where are we with the pathways acting on glucagon?*)," *Medecine des Maladies Metaboliques*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 16–21, Feb. 2018, doi: 10.1016/S1957-2557(18)30004-X.
- [24] M. E. Fisher, "A Semiclosed-Loop Algorithm for the Control of Blood Glucose Levels in Diabetics," *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 57–61, 1991, doi: 10.1109/10.68209.
- [25] M. G. Markakis, G. D. Mitsis, G. P. Papavasilopoulos, P. A. Ioannou, and V. Z. Marmarelis, "A switching control strategy for the attenuation of blood glucose disturbances," *Optimal Control Applications and Methods*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 185–195, Mar. 2011, doi: 10.1002/oca.900.
- [26] S. M. Lynch and B. W. Bequette, "Model predictive control of blood glucose in type I diabetes using subcutaneous glucose measurements," in *Proceedings of the American Control Conference, IEEE*, 2002, pp. 4039–4043, doi: 10.1109/ACC.2002.1024561.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Meriem Samai received the Bachelor's degree in Automatic Control in 2015, and the Master's degree in Automatic Control with a specialization in Industrial Process Control in 2017, both from Setif University, Algeria. She is currently pursuing a Ph.D. degree in Automatic Control at the same university. Her current research interests include adaptive control, glucose-insulin regulation, nonlinear systems, and robust control. She can be contacted at email: meriem.samai@univ-setif.dz.

Ghedjati Keltoum received the Engineering and the Magister degree in Automatic Control from the Setif University, Algeria in 2000 and 2008, and the Ph.D. degree in Automatic Control from Setif University, Algeria, in 2018. She is currently an Associate Professor at the Department of Automatic control, setif university, Algeria. Her current research interests include glucose insulin regulation, adaptive control, and unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV). She can be contacted at email: ghedjati.keltoum@univ-setif.dz.

Abdelaziz Mourad received the Engineering degree in Electrical Engineering from the Setif University, Algeria, in 1989 and the Magister degree in Automatic Control in 1992 from the Constantine University, and the Ph.D. degree in Automatic Control from Setif University, Algeria, in 2007. He is currently a Professor at the Department of Automatic Control, Setif University, Algeria. His current research interests include glucose insulin regulation, adaptive control, and unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV), He can be contacted at email: abdelaziz.mourad@univ-setif.dz, abde_m@yahoo.fr.